

Results of the ZKI Top Trends survey for the ZKI Strategy and Governance Working Group 2022

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Abstract

The working group on “Strategy and Organisation” of the ZKI Association for German academic IT centres conducts an annual survey on the most important topics and focal points of member institutions. The core survey takes up and documents the most relevant or trending issues of IT facilities from universities and research institutions. The results are intended to help keep an eye on important developments and best practices and to keep pace with the extensive topic of digitalisation and the rapid renewal of technologies, or to gain inspiration for further strategy and service design at one's own institution.

The survey is completed by CIOs, heads of data centres, IT directors and persons in comparable roles. The 2022 survey, carried out in December 2021 and January 2022 and completed by 85 institutions, had an additional focus on the enhanced use of cloud technologies, on digital sovereignty and on aspects of mobile work, changes in work routines and workplace design. Thus, the survey also addresses the medium- to long-term impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on IT institutions. The results might also shed light on some effects of the pandemic on academic IT facilities in other EU countries – or serve as a basis for differentiation.

1 Summary

The digital transformation at universities and research institutions has undergone a considerable acceleration due to the pandemic. It is accompanied by the modernisation of IT structures and digital technologies used at universities and research institutions. This is reflected in the survey results, on the one hand, in significantly increased mentions of organisational and technological changes compared to previous years, and on the other hand, in mentions of changed collaboration and leadership models.

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However, due to the ever-increasing shortage of skilled workers, this year also shows signs of overheating due to insufficient capacities for even more or expanded services and, at the same time, due to higher demands on implementation speed and compliance. In this context, it is surprising that the topic of cooperation has been mentioned less than in recent years, despite more difficult overall constraints.

The use of cloud solutions has increased in every respect: both as an on-premises cloud and as the use of resources from external providers. For the first time, the use of cloud technologies for operations is also cited more frequently. The answers to this year's specific focus questions on the topic indicate that the majority of institutions make use of application delivery (SaaS) most often, followed by virtualised infrastructure as a service (IaaS). Only among larger institutions the impact of Schrems II and the pursuit of digital sovereignty can be observed, e.g. by a decrease in external cloud use.

As activities in the area of digital sovereignty, many survey participants mentioned enhanced discussions and training on this topic with university management and users in order to generate understanding for alternative products. Other institutions have reviewed their service portfolio and introduced open source solutions – often used within a two-track model initially, i.e. parallel to solutions from large commercial providers. The need for "freedom of choice" with regard to applications in the course of freedom of research and teaching is emphasized particularly for academia. Furthermore, the successful history of cooperation among universities and research institutions are pointed out, as are the role and availability of in-house developers who can contribute to further development of open source applications.

Remote work and the acceptance of remote work routines continue to increase and will remain even after the pandemic. The majority of responses show an expectation of two to three days of remote work from home per week also for the future. In addition to extended requirements for hybrid workplaces and necessary multiple equipment for employees – and higher costs associated with this – a general flexibilisation of office environments is reported, beyond the classic use of workplaces by a single person. In addition to clean desk policies as a precondition for a flexible use of office space, additional equipment, e.g. with audio/video components, is also mentioned, as well as the need for an increased standardisation of these components in order to be able to guarantee support for them.

The approaches for ensuring data protection and IT security as well as for network management are subject to completely new technical challenges due to more flexible access options. These are necessary for the administrative units as well to secure working from home. The participants' response on the aspects "new work", leadership challenges or enabling informal communication show a more systematic involvement with the changes in the world of work brought about by the pandemic. The importance of video conferencing is seen as fundamental to remote work and consequential forms of collaboration. Chat and collaboration solutions are other frequently mentioned concrete tools. A greater need for transparency in the provision of information is generally noted. And, moreover, the use of project management tools is emphasised in this context. Face-to-face meetings for team building, occasional on-site work, having lunch together and meetings in smaller groups in the office once in a while are methods mentioned for maintaining personal togetherness.

Most survey participants discern a strengthened role of IT at the institution. Likewise, a higher awareness within the HEI for additional investments in digitalisation and IT is reported as a change in attitudes. As emphasised in the responses, IT institutions are more often than before seen as playing a partner or key role in the design and support of digitalisation and change at their institutions. This development goes hand in hand with higher expectations of the users and higher demands on compliance. Despite the expanded tasks, staff resources are described as largely constant or precarious.

The relevant top trends in 2022 for the ZKI community are the topics:

Figure 1: Relevant top trends - 140 mentions from 44 institutions

The annual core survey asks on the one hand about general IT trends and on the other hand about trends of particular relevance to the own institution (cf. Fig. 1). The trends with the highest relevance for the institutions are shown here. More so than in previous years, the mentions for general and relevant trends are largely identical this year. Only for the topic of staff shortages, the individual relevance is rated higher, presumably due to its direct impact on one's own institution for almost all activities. The opposite is true for the topic of machine learning, which is rated higher as a general trend than for one's own institution. Research data management is no longer mentioned frequently at this point, but it is in second place among the strategic topics[†]. This might imply, the topic of research data management is now more strongly integrated as a regular part of the services offered by the IT centres.

2 Special focus 2022

While the focus in last year's 2021 survey was more generally on the direct impact of the pandemic, for 2022 there is a focus of questions on cloud solutions, digital sovereignty, remote work and, generally speaking, certain expectable medium- to long-term impact of the pandemic on IT centres.

Has the use of external cloud solutions increase or decrease during the pandemic?

The results show a significant increase in the use of external cloud solutions as a result of accelerated requirements in digitalisation during the pandemic.

[†] Dreyer, Malte. (2022). Ergebnisse der ZKI Top Trends-Umfrage des ZKI-Arbeitskreises Strategie und Organisation für das Jahr 2022 (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6012936>

Figure 2: Change in the use of cloud solutions (n=71)

The following graphs show the distribution of responses by type and size of institution.

Figure 3: Change in the use of cloud solutions by type of institution (n=71)

Figure 4: Change in the use of cloud solutions by size of institution (n=71)

The results show that larger institutions tend to take a more differentiated approach to the use of external cloud solutions, as might also have been expected as an impact of the Schrems II ruling. Nevertheless, overall, there is a huge increase in the use of external cloud solutions across all types and sizes of institutions.

To what extent do you use cloud technologies?

The question is aimed at the type of cloud technologies used at the institutions. A distinction is made between IaaS, PaaS and SaaS solutions[‡].

[‡] https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cloud_Computing

Figure 5: Type of cloud usage by type of service and on-site or off-site operation (n=84)

Unsurprisingly, the use of SaaS solutions, in which individual applications are provided locally or externally, predominates overall. The use of IaaS and PaaS follow at some distance.

The respective use of infrastructure, platform and software provision services shows the following distribution.

Figure 6: Use of Infrastructure as a Service

Most IaaS cloud solutions are established as a private cloud at the institution itself. Around one third of the institutions also rely on external services for the provision of basic IT resources.

Figure 7: Use of Platform as a Service

PaaS cloud solutions are also predominantly operated on-site. Around a third of the institutions rely on the use of platforms from external providers.

Figure 8: Use of Software as a Service

SaaS solutions, on the other hand, are predominantly used as services from external providers outside the institution itself.

Comparing the use depending on the type and size of the facility yields the following results.

Figure 9: Use of cloud solutions by type of institution (n=84)

Figure 10: Use of cloud solutions with regard to size of the institution (n=84)

What measures have you taken in the area of "digital sovereignty"?

The answers to this question are partly contradictory. The majority describe an intensification of discussions and training on the topic of digital sovereignty with university management and users in order to generate a better understanding for the use of alternative products, among other things. Other institutions have reviewed their service portfolio and introduced open source solutions – often initially in a two-track model, parallel to solutions from the large commercial providers. New projects are often mentioned that are intended to systematically create alternatives to the solutions of large providers for a higher sovereignty of one's own institution. The focus here is usually on productivity platforms, private clouds and solutions for video conferencing.

The answers in detail (from 33 institutions):

- Create awareness in the university management
- Two-pronged product strategy
- Offers of data-minimisation systems as an alternative
- Expansion of the video portal
- Expansion of open-source services on-premises
- Discussion of the topic in committees and cooperation networks
- Discussions about alternatives
- Discussions about licensing models and costs
- More open source
- Development of a project for a web-based workplace
- Establishment of data categories
- Evaluation of alternatives for MS products
- Intensive use of group policies, especially with MS products
- Intensification of training for more digital competence
- Investment in open source
- Cooperations for app development
- More trainings
- More service delivery on-premises
- Nextcloud
- Onlyoffice
- Open source where possible
- "Workplace of the Future" project reviewed
- Project for Open Source Productivity Platform
- Project to replace Office 365 started
- Testing of alternatives

- Testing for open source alternatives
- Legal advice sought for options
- Raising the awareness for digital sovereignty in the board
- Training of employees
- Strategic reassessment of the service portfolio
- Extensive "Private Cloud" project launched
- Stronger focus to avoid vendor lock-in

What specific aspects do you see for universities and research institutions in the area of digital sovereignty?

25 institutions contributed to this question. The need for "freedom of choice" of applications in the course of freedom of research and teaching, the successful experiences of universities and research institutions in cooperating with each other as well as the availability of own developers who can be used for further development of open source applications are emphasised. Another aspect is the increasing dependence on the costs for individual providers – especially licensing costs – which, without proper alternatives, might lead to a situation similar to that of journal subscriptions in the area of information provision. In addition, a growing isolation of structures and projects of the institutions is cited, which stands in the way of a cooperative addressing of needs in larger groups, or makes the formation of larger alliances to negotiate with commercial providers more difficult. The excessive workload caused by the lack of skilled workers and the higher pressure to implement solutions also stands in the way of the formation of cooperations and the division of labour in service provision.

The answers in detail:

- Creation and promotion of alternatives
- Dependencies on a few providers
- Special requirements for data protection
- Reducing reservations about digitalised processes
- Dependencies on suppliers outside the EU
- Moving away from commercial products unrealistic
- Create alternatives to Office 365
- Clarification of the background
- Finding a balance between on-site operations and complete outsourcing
- Ensure data sovereignty
- Digital sovereignty must be implemented more consistently and promoted politically
- Own developers available
- Lack of investment in the sustainability of open source
- Maintain flexibility
- Focus on on-premises solutions and open source software

- Researchers must use platforms to cooperate internationally
- Preserve capacity to act
- High costs for software systems
- Do not use certain products in teaching
- No special features - every facility depends on software
- Uncompromising data protection
- Consistent digitalisation
- Enable cost control
- Teachers demand commercial, possibly non-data-saving tools
- Rental instead of purchase licences cause higher costs
- Splitting users into 2 groups: Change of software and concrete need for specific products
- Strengths of the universities lie in cooperation and joint development
- Stronger cooperation is desirable
- Switching to cloud solutions prevents control over data
- Vendor Lock-In
- Avoidance of vendor lock-in
- Use of open source strengthens digital sovereignty
- Freedom of choice of solutions within the framework of "freedom of research and teaching".
- Restoring the foundations of a market economy
- Too many individual activities, which on the one hand prevent larger negotiating alliances and on the other hand prevent larger investments in open source.

What impact do you estimate Corona to have on workplace design?

There were answers to this question from 46 institutions.

Mobile working and its acceptance continue to increase and will remain so even after the pandemic. This view is shared by many survey participants. As a result, the share of notebook use is increasing and desktop systems are becoming less important. In addition to extended requirements for hybrid workplaces and multiple equipment being necessary for employees (and the associated higher costs), a general flexibilisation of the use of office environments is also reported, which goes beyond the classic use of workplaces by a single person. In addition to clean desk policies as a precondition for a more flexible use of office space, additional equipment with audio/video components is also mentioned, as well as the need for greater standardisation for these in order to be able to guarantee support for all components. Increased demand on collaboration solutions and virtualised, location-independent telephone options are also mentioned, as are problems working with the usually smaller display sizes of notebooks compared to stationary monitors.

The approaches for ensuring data protection and IT security as well as for network management are subject to completely new technical challenges due to the more flexible access options, which are also necessary in the administrative area with cloud use from home. A complete reorganisation of the

technical concepts is often mentioned in this regard. The importance of providing high-performance VPN resources by the institutions and a sufficient network connection for work from home are just as much a prerequisite for location-independent work as a more specific and at the same time more flexible control of access mechanisms and policies.

Dealing with "New Work", leadership challenges and issues of enabling informal communication are further responses and show a more systematic involvement with the changes in the world of work due to the pandemic and due to accelerated digitalisation.

There are also reports of delivery problems for products in the mobile workplace environment in many areas.

Answer	Count
Mobile work is increasing	15
Increased use of notebooks	6
Flexible workplaces at the university become necessary	5
Higher requirements for IT security	3
Shared Desk workplace models	3
Higher relevance of "New Work"	2
Hybrid workplace models	2
More work from home	2
Mobile working will stay	2
Fewer desktop computers	2

What tools and mechanisms have helped you maintain collaboration and team spirit despite less presence at the work place?

There were responses from 42 institutions to this question.

The importance of video conferencing is seen as fundamental to mobile working and the form of collaboration that goes with it. Chat and collaboration solutions in general are other concrete tools that are mentioned very frequently. However, ticket systems, desktop sharing and wikis are also mentioned for improved knowledge management and more structured processes, as well as a general need for greater transparency in the provision of information. In this context, project management tools are also highlighted as a means for more transparency while at the same time improving the basis for the structured implementation of projects.

Face-to-face meetings for team-building, occasional on-site work, lunch together and meetings in smaller groups in the office are answers to how the preservation of personal togetherness can be brought about.

In the context of changed leadership methodology, open door models are also mentioned, in which, for example, a video conference remains regularly open as an open office hour for any topics. A trend towards shorter but more frequent meetings is also reported, e.g. daily instead of weekly meetings. Virtual coffee breaks are a model for informal exchange at team level. All-hands meetings, where all employees of an area or the whole IT centre meet regularly for cross-cutting reports, are mentioned as a low-threshold method for better information flow and more visibility for all people and issues.

Answer	Count
Video conferencing	31
Chat	19
Collaboration platforms	9
Daily meetings	5

Shorter meetings	4
Joint lunch breaks	2
More frequent team meetings per VC	2
Kanban	2
Newsletter	2
Project management software	2
Regular meeting dates	2
Ticket systems	2
Virtual coffee breaks	2
Wikis	2
Zoom	2

What percentage of home office do you see in the future for your university's IT facility?

The responses show an expectation of two to three days of mobile work per week even after the pandemic. The shares of responses with more than three days or only one day of mobile work taken together only make up about 23% of the responses.

Figure 11: Estimated share of mobile work – distribution (n=72)

How do you see the role of IT at your university after Corona?

Of the 46 institutions that responded to this question, 27 report an overall strengthening of the role of IT at the institution – just under 60%. Another change frequently mentioned is a higher awareness within the higher education institution for additional investments in digitalisation and IT. It has also become clearer that IT will be more cost-intensive with the increased requirements. In the responses, IT institutions are more often than before given a partner or key role in designing and supporting digitalisation and change at the institutions. This goes hand in hand with higher user expectations, higher compliance requirements for operations in general and for IT security and data protection in particular – also due to more mobile working. Many institutions describe the challenge that demands on IT, number of tasks, expectations regarding the speed of implementation and rapid provision of new solutions have all increased, but personnel resources for those tasks have remained largely constant despite the equally increased compliance requirements, or are even described as precarious.

Answer	Count
Strengthened	27
Need for investment in digitalisation becomes more obvious	7
Unchanged	7
More tasks with the same resources	6
Higher requirements for IT security	3
More competition between the IT sectors	2

3 Changes in the top trends compared to the previous year

These questions are intended to shed light on how the top trends relevant to IT institutions at universities and research institutions change over the years.

Compared to the previous year, the top trends have changed as follows:

Figure 12: Change in top trends compared to 2021 results sorted by top mentions in 2021 (n=81)

The trends with increasing importance are:

Figure 13: Top topics with increasing importance sorted by number of mentions (n=81)

The following chart, based on the most frequent responses, shows how the topics have changed in their rankings within the top trends between 2018 and 2022.

Trend	Top-Trends Position				
	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018
Information Security	1	2	1	2	5
Digitalisation	5	3	3	1	1
Cloud	2	1	2	6	4
Research Data		10	7	3	2
Machine learning	6	11	4	5	
Cooperation	11	8	5	4	7
Staff shortage	3	9	6	9	
Virtualisation			9		9
Data Protection	7	4			
Work from home	4	6			
Digital Sovereignty	9	5			